

LANGUAGE MEANS OF REALIZING THE TOURIST PICTURE OF THE WORLD AND THE CONCEPT OF TOURISM

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Abstract. The global tourism space, which is globalizing along with the globalization of population and culture, is a conceptual cognitive-communicative space, the cultural meanings of which are verbalized in the concepts of tourism.

Key words: concept, cultural tourism, conceptual space, context, international tourism, intercultural communication.

The concepts of international tourism as operational meaningful units of memory, the main cells of culture in the mental world of a person, symbols and markers of the tourist space form a system of concepts that is an ordered hierarchical set of universal cultural, national cultural (ethno-cultural), universal tourism industry and national tourism industry concepts.

One of the key concepts of modern international tourism is the concept of "cultural tourism". Despite the existing approach, which consists in the fact that in modern conditions of a globalizing multicultural world, any type of international tourism can be called cultural, as it is associated with crossing national borders, temporary residence in other cultural communities, intercultural interaction and communication between "guests" and "hosts". ", as well as "guests" from different cultures on the territory of the "hosts", "cultural tourism" is distinguished into an independent form according to a number of conceptual features.

As the analysis of the factual material showed, the terms of international tourism in terms of structural and grammatical features can be represented by terms-words and terminological phrases (or quasi-terms).

The terms-words of the analyzed sphere are represented by non-derivatives (for example, tour, hotel, season, cruise, resort, etc.), derivatives (for example,

tourist, tourism, tourist, off-season, cruise, resort, balneology, etc.).) and complex (for example, travel agent, tour package, inclusive tour, apart-hotel, etc.) nominations. Abbreviation terms should also be referred to this structural type. The terminology of international tourism is characterized by both Russian: ATOR (Association of Tour Operators of Russia), and foreign language abbreviations that are completely borrowed from English while maintaining the Latin script: ARR (arrival), DEP (departure, departure), CIT (charter inclusive tour) , FIT (tour including flight). Such abbreviations are intended to serve operational activities in international tourism. Abbreviations of organizations and associations in tourism can function in specialized texts in double spelling - Cyrillic and Latin: WTO (World Tourism Organization) and WTO.

Research in the field of terminology confirms the fact that the formed terminological system of any field of knowledge contains about 70% of terms-phrases (multi-component terms)

Multi-component terms in the modern Russian terminological system of international tourism can be two-word, three-word and multi-word (consisting of four or more components).

Two-component (two-word) terms-phrases are represented by substantive terminological units built according to the following grammatical models:

1) Noun + Adjective (Compare, for example, dark tourism, business tourism; single ticket, baggage check, boarding pass, charter flight, tourism industry, etc.).

Compare also: full fare - the declared maximum price for the carriage of passengers and their baggage (IMTT); baggage receipt - an official document confirming that the airline has taken over the carriage of the passenger's baggage and issued it at the end of the carriage (IMTT); single ticket - bus and ferry transportation system (IMTS);

2) Noun (in the nominative case) + Noun (in the indirect case (Compare, for example, the terms tourism industry, reception desk, waiting list, airfare, date of arrival, etc.).

Compare also: arrival card - a special form filled out by a passenger arriving in another country and handed over at a border control post (IMTT); excess baggage - excess baggage in excess of the limit established by the airline, the carriage of which is paid by the passenger additionally (IMTT); hotel category - an assessment of the level of the hotel, based on a set of requirements for buildings, material and technical equipment, the quality of services provided and the level of service (IMTS); peak season - the period of the greatest workload of the holiday destination (IMTT).

There are also phrase-terms built according to the model Noun + Preposition + Noun (for example, tourism insurance, contract with a tourist, booking request, room service, shopping tour, etc.) in the area under study.

Преобладание именных терминов - словосочетаний над глагольными в терминологии международного туризма обусловлено, по мнению целого ряда исследователей, тем, что они обладают наиболее отчетливыми систематизирующими свойствами и принципиальной способностью заполнять гипонимические позиции в терминологических микросистемах.

In addition to the substantive terms of the tourism sector, verbal nominations are also noted (for example, make a transplant, deliver tourists, pay the bill, etc.).

Two-component terms-phrases can be reduced to two main varieties - free and non-free.

In free phrases, each of the components is a term or is motivated by a term, and their components can enter into two-way communication (eg, hospitality industry, tourism industry, tourism management, tour operating management, tourism marketing, etc.).

Compare: the hospitality industry is a kind of tourist service, which is based on the principles of hospitality, characterized by generosity and friendliness towards guests (BGTMT); tour operating management - a system of measures aimed at solving the issues of managing the activities of tour operators in the tourism business and the relations of tour operators with producers of tourist services, intermediaries

and consumers of a tourist product (ST); tourism manager - a specialist who provides the development of tours and the organization of tourist services on tourist routes (ST).

In non-free phrases, all components or one of them can be non-terms (for example, outbound tourism, treatment tour, off season, hotel chain, etc.).

Compare: the off season is the period of the least tourist attendance of a certain region (SMTT); chain (chain) of hotels - a group of hotels engaged in collective business (SMTT); outbound tourism is the activity of residents of a country traveling through the territory of another country (ST).

Some researchers distinguish the third structural type of terminological nominations among terms-phrases - symbol-words, which include certain symbols (graphic signs or numbers) (for example, a three-star hotel, etc.).

Studies have shown that a two-component nominal phrase is the most common type of compound terms in the field of international tourism. Such terms consist of a combination of a noun in the nominative case as the main component and an adjective as a dependent word. Less common are terms - phrases with the participle of the present tense in the role of a prepositive definition, which become carriers not of a procedural (temporary), but rather of a specific feature of the noun being defined (for example, complementary programs, host, etc.).

Among the compound terms, a model with a numeral as a defining element was also identified (for example, first class, second class, third class; first line, second line, etc.).

Three-word (three-component) terms-phrases of the studied sphere are built on the main types of syntactic connection - coordination and management (for example, the motivation of tourist activities, accommodation facilities in tourism, etc.), however, a compositional connection between the two components of the compound term is also possible (for example, booking and reservation system, time for games and entertainment, recreation and service area, payment for accommodation and meals, permission to enter and leave, etc.).

Thus, a large number of terms-phrases is associated with the acceleration of the process of specialization of tourist terms, the formation of the hierarchy and structure of the terminological system, and the consolidation of derivational relations between terms.

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